

Choice of Matrix System for Class II Composite Restoration; a Cross Sectional Survey among the Dentists of Multan Dental College

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ABSTRACT

Since last two decades composite material has been very famous for the restoration of posterior teeth. Formation of contact area mimicking natural contact area remained always challenging for a dentist in a posterior class II composite restoration. Objective of this study is to evaluate preference of dentists to use different matrix system for class II composite restoration. This cross sectional survey has been conducted in Multan dental college after taking informed consent from the dentists. A questionnaire was distributed among eighty five participants who included graduates, post graduate residents and post graduates. Three options for matrix system had been given to the participants; A=Universal matrix system or tofflemire, B=Sectional matrix system, C= Sectional matrix system with separating rings or palodent system. Forty were males and forty five were females included in the study (Table 1). Forty two graduates, thirty two post graduates and eleven post graduates residents filled the questionnaire (Table 1). Most of the participants (51%) were in favor of using universal matrix band and few (20%) were in favor of using sectional matrix system with separating rings (Table 2). Conclusion of the study is that most of the participants preferred universal matrix system due to ease in application and low cost. For graduates and general practitioners there is strong need of awareness regarding use of modern matrix system.

Key words: Composite, Contacts and Contours, Class II restoration, Matrix system.

INTRODUCTION

Since last two decades composite material has been very famous for the restoration of posterior teeth.^{1, 2} Although amalgam have better strength than composite³ but mercury toxicity and esthetic requirement reduced the utilization of amalgam in dentistry⁴. Recent innovations in dental materials make the composites stronger for posterior restoration⁵.

Formation of contact area mimicking natural contact area remained always challenging for a dentist in a posterior class II composite restoration⁶. Health of periodontal tissues always depends upon tight contact area of restoration which prevents the impaction of food⁷. Inappropriate interproximal contact area of restoration can cause gingival inflammation which leads to periodontitis and loss of alveolar bone.⁸ Patients have felt pain and discomfort on chewing if dentist fails to make proper contact area of restoration with proximal tooth.⁹ Interproximal contact point should not too much tight to pass dental floss.¹⁰ On contrary to amalgam, composite restoration cannot be condensed against matrix and proximal surface of adjacent tooth which results in formation of open contact area.¹¹

Recent advancement in the field of dental materials introduced packable composites which had improved condensing ability than conventional composites. These advancement includes the use of glass inserts, pre-polymerized resins and increased size of filler components^{12,13}. These changes in the composites not only reduce the polymerization shrinkage but also improve the condensing ability of the material which help in making

proper contact and contour¹⁴. Proper contact and contour are two primary features should be present on the proximal surface of restoration¹⁵. Beyond the advancement of composite materials, special instruments has also been launched in the market for class II composite restoration which mainly comprised of different matrix systems, wedges, separation rings and contoured bands. Many matrices systems are present to make proper contact point. Some of these are universal matrix system, sectional matrix band with separating ring, T-band, and automatrix etc¹⁶.

The objective of this study is to evaluate preference of dentists to use different matrix system for class II composite restoration.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This cross-sectional survey has been conducted in Multan dental college after taking informed consent from the dentists. A questionnaire was distributed among eighty-five participants who included graduates, post graduate residents and post graduates. Three options for matrix system had been given to the participants; A=Universal matrix system or tofflemire, B=Sectional matrix system, C= Sectional matrix system with separating rings or palodent system.

RESULTS

Forty were males and forty five were females included in the study (Table 1). Forty two graduates, thirty two post graduates and eleven post graduates residents filled the questionnaire (Table 1). Most of the participants (51%) were in favor of using universal matrix band and few (20%) were in favor of using sectional matrix system with separating rings (Table 2).

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Table 1: Distribution of participants according to Gender and Qualification.

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	40	48%
	Female	45	52%
Qualification	Graduates	42	49%
	Post graduates	32	38%
	Post graduate residents	11	13%

Table 2: Distribution on the basis of qualification.

Categories	Graduates	Post graduates	Post graduate residents	Total
A=Universal matrix system or tofflemire	30(72%)	8(25%)	5(45%)	43(51%)
B=Sectional matrix system	9(21%)	14(44%)	2(19%)	25(29%)
C= Sectional matrix system with separating rings or palodent system	3(7%)	10(31%)	4(36%)	17(20%)

DISCUSSION

Anterior and posterior teeth should be restored with composites because composites have good mechanical strength and esthetics. Proximal contact and contour still has little problem to build properly instead of advancement in instruments for composite restoration and matrix system.¹⁷ In present study most of the dentist(51%) still believed that tofflemire retainer had accomplished the requirement for building the proper contact and contour. In study of UK 61% dentists believed that tofflemire was the choice of retainer in the posterior composite class II restoration.¹⁸ This proportion is higher than that of my study because in the study of UK most of the participants were general dentist but in present study 51% dentist are general dentist. Tofflemire matrix system is cost effective and easy to use that is why most of the dentists prefer this system. Most of dental schools in the world taught tofflemire matrix system more often than others¹⁷. According to survey 94% American schools and 88% schools of United Kingdom studied tofflemire matrix system while only 59% American and 47% UK schools taught sectional matrix system.¹⁹ A study was conducted in United State Air Force dental facility centre where 58% dentist experienced about tofflemire retainer which is similar to current study²⁰. Farah stated that in Lahore 65% dentists preferred tofflemire matrix system for class II composite restoration which is higher than that of present study (51%)¹⁷.

In the study of Farah fifty percent general dentist used tofflemire while in present study 72% general dentist used tofflemire retainers. In present study 25% graduates adopted to this type of retainer and in the study of Farah more than forty percent post graduates relied on this retainer¹⁷.

In the present study 29% dentist adopted sectional matrix band without retainer because sectional matrix band were formed better anatomy of tooth due to precontoured shape²¹. In current study 44% post graduates used precontoured sectional matrix band because they have knowledge that precontoured shaped matrix band formed better contour of the tooth than sectional matrix bands. In the study of United State Air Force Dental Facility Centre 86% of the dentists were experienced in sectional matrix band because that centre was better equipped with modern instruments and materials²⁰. In the study of Farah 24% dentist used sectional matrix bands which was similar to the results of current study¹⁷.

In this study 20 % dentists were relied on sectional matrix band with separating rings or palodent system. In this proportion most of post graduates (31%) and post graduate trainees (36%) used that system but few graduates (7%) adopted palodent system. Palodent system provides more tight contact point than any other system²¹. In this system contour of restorations had more resemblance to natural tooth contour due to sectional matrix band. In our institutes palodent system is not practiced much due to its high cost and complex procedure than tofflemire¹⁷. In the study of Farah 10 % general practitioner used palodent system while in current study this proportion declined to 7%. In current study fourteen out of seventeen palodent users were post graduate trainees and post graduates which were similar to the study of Farah (88%)¹⁷.

Many surveys conducted in the past for reporting the quality of contact point and contour of proximal restoration with different type of retainers^{21,22}. Most of researches were satisfied with the performance of Palodent system than others²¹⁻²⁵. Palodent system provides more tight contact point and proper contour of proximal restoration so that our graduates should prefer modern matrix system for class II composite restoration.

CONCLUSION

In current study most of the participants preferred universal matrix system due to ease in application and low cost. For graduates and general practitioners there is strong need of awareness regarding use of modern matrix system.

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